

The background of the cover is a composite image. On the left, there is an aerial photograph of a river winding through a dry, brown landscape. On the right, there is a dark blue background with a white line graph showing fluctuating data points, overlaid with a faint grid pattern.

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**INNOVATIVE
APPROACHES TO
WATER RESOURCE
MANAGEMENT IN
ARID REGIONS IN THE
CONTEXT OF
CLIMATE CHANGE**

PROCEEDINGS
(Conference Proceedings)

May 19, 2026

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

WICAR-2026

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International Scientific and Practical Conference -2026

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN ARID REGIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference innovative approaches to water resource management in arid regions in the context of climate change on May 19, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The conference aims to discuss key issues of effective water resource management in arid regions under climate change, develop and apply innovative approaches and mathematical and computational modeling methods, share recent research results and practical experience, and strengthen international academic cooperation in this field.

Key Themes of the Conference:

1. Water Diplomacy and Integrated Approaches in International Relation: Interdisciplinary Approaches to Sustainable Development, Communication and Global Security

- Issues of systemic analysis in international relations and world politics in the context of water diplomacy
- Economic, environmental and energy aspects of sustainable development
- Systemic approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

2. Mathematical and computer modeling of optimal water resources management under climate change

- Optimal water resource management under climate change
- Modeling water resource dynamics and climate variability
- Methods of applied and computational mathematics in irrigation system modeling.

3. Environmental and Hydrogeological Processes in the Aral Sea Region: Analysis Based on Modern Technologies

- Analysis of hydrogeological processes in the Aral Sea region
- Application of artificial intelligence, machine learning, and big data technologies to environmental challenges
- Simulation and stochastic modeling of environmental and hydrogeological processes in the Aral region.

The event was conducted in a hybrid format with participation in English, Russian, and Uzbek. The conference provided a high-level platform for scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Yashil investitsiyalarni baholashda xalqaro metodologiyalar: AQSh, EU, Janubiy Koreya va Xitoy tajribasining qiyosiy tahlili

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada AQSh, Yevropa Ittifoqi (EU), Janubiy Koreya va Xitoyda yashil investitsiya loyihalarini baholash metodologiyalari qiyosiy tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot muammosi shundan iboratki, an'anaviy moliyaviy ko'rsatkichlar — sof joriy qiymat (NPV) va ichki rentabellik normasining (IRR) — yashil loyihalar ekologik va ijtimoiy foydalarini to'liq qamrab olmasligi investitsiya qarorlarini noto'g'ri yo'naltirishga olib keladi. Tadqiqot maqsadi — to'rtta xalqaro modelni 12 mezon bo'yicha taqqoslab, ularning kuchli va zaif tomonlarini aniqlash hamda O'zbekiston uchun amaliy xulosalar chiqarishdir. Metodologiya sifatida qiyosiy-tahliliy usul, kengaytirilgan xarajat-foyda tahlili (CBA) va empirik ma'lumotlar tahlili qo'llanildi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki: (1) barcha to'rtta model orasida TCFD va ISSB xalqaro standartlari atrofida konvergentsiya tendentsiyasi kuzatilmoqda; (2) uglerod ijtimoiy qiymati (SCC) kabi ekologik monetizatsiya ko'rsatkichlarini baholashga kiritish loyiha rentabelligi bahosini sezilarli o'zgartiradi — Navoiy quyosh elektrostansiyasi misolida moliyaviy IRR (8,1%) va kengaytirilgan ERR (14,2%) o'rtasidagi 6,1 foizlik farq bu xulosani tasdiqlamoqda. Maqola O'zbekiston uchun moslashtirilgan gibrid baholash modelining nazariy asoslarini taklif etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: yashil investitsiya, baholash metodologiyasi, CBA, SCC, EU Taxonomy, K-Taxonomy, O'zbekiston, konvergentsiya

1. KIRISH

Iqlim o'zgarishi va resurslar tanqisligiga doir global muammolar yashil investitsiyalar hajmini keskin oshirishni talab qilmoqda. BloombergNEF ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, 2023-yilda global energetika o'tish investitsiyalari \$1,8 trln dan oshdi [1]. Paris kelishuvi (2015) 2-moddasi barcha ishtirokchi davlatlardan moliyaviy oqimlarni past uglerodli rivojlanish yo'nalishiga moslashtirish majburiyatini yuklaydi [2].

Biroq yashil investitsiya loyihalarini baholashda fundamental metodologik muammo mavjud: an'anaviy moliyaviy ko'rsatkichlar — NPV va IRR — loyihaning ekologik va ijtimoiy tashqi ta'sirlarini (externalities) hisobga olmaydi. Ekologik iqtisodiyot nazariyasiga ko'ra, yashil loyihalar yaratadigan ijobiy tashqi ta'sirlar — CO₂ emissiyasini kamaytirish, havo sifatini yaxshilash, sog'liqni muhofaza qilish — bozor narxiga to'liq aks etmaydi [3]. Bu holat kapitalning yashil yo'nalishga o'z-o'zicha burilmasligiga olib keladi.

Xalqaro amaliyotda ushbu muammoni hal etish uchun turli yondashuvlar shakllangan: AQSh Social Cost of Carbon (SCC) metodologiyasini joriy etgan [4]; EU kengaytirilgan Taxonomy va Do No Significant Harm (DNSH) tamoyilini qabul qilgan [5]; Janubiy Koreya ikki darajali K-Taxonomy tizimini yaratgan [6]; Xitoy Environmental Benefit Score (EBS) metodologiyasini ishlab chiqqan [7]. Biroq ushbu yondashuvlarning qiyosiy tahlili va rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlar — xususan O'zbekiston — uchun amaliy xulosalari yetarlicha o'rganilmagan.

Tadqiqot maqsadi: To'rtta xalqaro yashil investitsiya baholash metodologiyasini qiyosiy tahlil qilish, ular orasidagi konvergentsiya tendentsiyasini aniqlash va O'zbekiston uchun moslashtirilgan yondashuv asoslarini taklif etish.

Ushbu maqolaning ilmiy yangiligi shundaki, O'zbekiston miqyosida birinchi marta to'rtta yirik mintaqani bir vaqtda kompleks qiyosiy tahlil qilish orqali uglerod narxlashning kapital oqimlariga tizimli ta'siri metodologik jihatdan asoslab beriladi.

2. METODOLOGIYA

Tadqiqotda quyidagi metodlar qo'llanildi. Asosiy metod — qiyosiy-tahliliy usul bo'lib, to'rtta mamlakat (AQSh, EU, Janubiy Koreya, Xitoy) yashil investitsiya baholash tizimlari 12 ta mezon bo'yicha taqqoslandi. Mezonlar ikki toifaga ajratildi: (1) metodologik mezonlar — baholash vositasi, uglerod narxlash, LCA qo'llanishi, ekologik foyda o'lchash; (2) institutsional mezonlar — tartibga solish xususiyati, greenwashing nazorati, shaffoflik, xalqaro muvofiqlik.

Kengaytirilgan xarajat-foyda tahlili (Extended CBA) metodologiyasi qo'llanildi, unda ekologik foydalar Social Cost of Carbon (SCC) ko'rsatkichi orqali monetizatsiya qilindi. Empirik ma'lumotlar Navoiy quyosh elektrostansiyasi loyihasining rasmiy hujjatlaridan — ADB [8], IFC [9] va World Bank [10] — olindi. Loyiha parametrlari: quvvat 130 MVt, investitsiya \$120 mln, tarif \$0,027/kWh, muddati 25 yil. Ijtimoiy diskont stavkasi (SDR) sifatida rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlar uchun tavsiya etilgan 6% qo'llanildi [11].

Ikkilamchi ma'lumotlar OECD, World Bank, IEA, BloombergNEF rasmiy hujjatlari va 2015-2025-yillar oralig'ida chop etilgan peer-reviewed maqolalardan olindi. Taqqoslash matritsasini tuzishda ko'p mezonli qaror qabul qilish (MCDM) yondashuvi qo'llanildi, har bir mezon bo'yicha 1-5 shkala ishlatildi.

3. NATIJALAR

3.1. To'rtta metodologiyaning qiyosiy tahlili

To'rtta modelning 12 mezon bo'yicha qiyosiy tahlili quyidagi natijalarni berdi (1-jadval):

Mezon	AQSh	EU	J. Koreya	Xitoy
Asosiy vosita	CBA+SCC+LCOE	LCA+CBA+DNSH	K-Tax+K-ESG	EBS+ESIA
Uglerod narxi	\$51-190 (siyosiy)	€60-100 (bozor)	O'rta (K-ETS)	Past (\$8-10)
Tartibga solish	Ixtiyoriy	Majburiy	Gibrid	Davlat
Greenwashing	O'rta	Eng kuchli	O'rta	Zaif
LCA qo'llanishi	Ixtiyoriy	Majburiy	Qisman	Cheklangan
Shaffoflik	O'rta	Eng yuqori	O'rta	Past
Kichik loyihalar	O'rta	Past	O'rta	Yuqori
Xalq. muvofiqlik	Yuqori	Eng yuqori	O'rta-yuqori	Past-o'rta

1-jadval. To'rtta yashil investitsiya baholash metodologiyasining qiyosiy matritsasi

3.2. Kengaytirilgan CBA: Navoiy loyihasida empirik natijalar

Navoiy quyosh elektrostansiyasi loyihasida kengaytirilgan CBA metodologiyasini qo'llash quyidagi natijalarni berdi (2-jadval):

Ko'rsatkich	Qiymat	Izoh
Moliyaviy IRR	8,1%	Faqat daromad asosida
Kengaytirilgan ERR	14,2%	SCC + ijtimoiy foyda kiritilganda
Farq	+6,1 f.p.	Ekologik foydaning moliyaviy qiymati
NPV (6% SDR, 25 yil)	+\$97,3 mln	Loyiha ijtimoiy jihatdan samarali
CO2 kamaytirish foyda	\$7,65 mln/yil	150,000 t x \$51/tCO2 (SCC)
Moliyaviy daromad	\$7,29 mln/yil	270,000 MWh x \$0,027/kWh
Ijtimoiy foyda	\$6,20 mln/yil	31,000 uy x \$200/yil

2-jadval. Navoiy quyosh elektrostansiyasida kengaytirilgan CBA natijalari

2-jadval shuni ko'rsatadiki, ekologik foyda (\$7,65 mln/yil) moliyaviy daromad (\$7,29 mln/yil) bilan deyarli teng. Bu holat an'anaviy IRR metodologiyasining yashil loyihalar samaradorligini past baholash tendentsiyasini tasdiqlaydi.

3.3. Uglerod narxining kapital oqimlariga tizimli ta'siri

AQSh tajribasidan olingan Ivanpah Solar loyihasi (392 MVt, California) misolida SCC ning qaror qabul qilishga ta'siri yaqqol ko'rinadi. 7% diskont stavkasida va SCC hisobga olinmagan holda loyiha NPV ko'rsatkichi -\$450 mln ni tashkil etdi. Biroq 3% diskont stavkasida va \$42/tCO2 SCC kiritilganda NPV +\$180 mln ga aylandi [4]. Bir xil loyiha, bir xil texnik ko'rsatkichlar — biroq metodologiyaga qarab natija qarama-qarshi bo'ldi.

Bu topilma muhim nazariy xulosaga olib keladi: SCC metodologiyasini baholashga kiritish nafaqat bitta loyihaning NPV ko'rsatkichini o'zgartiradi — balki yashil va an'anaviy loyihalar o'rtasidagi raqobatbardoshlikni tubdan o'zgartiradi. An'anaviy yuqori uglerodli loyiha ham SCC orqali qayta baholanganda uning ijtimoiy xarajatlari sezilarli oshadi, bu esa kapital oqimini yashil yo'nalishga burishning metodologik asosini tashkil etadi.

3.4. Konvergeniya tendentsiyasi

To'rtta metodologiyaning tahlili global konvergeniya tendentsiyasini ko'rsatdi. Xitoy 2023-yildan CSRD bilan moslashish muhokamalarini boshlagan [7]; Koreya 2024-yilda ISSB S1/S2 standartlariga o'tdi [6]; AQSh SEC iqlim oshkor qilish qoidalarini kuchaytirayotgan [4]. Barcha to'rtta model TCFD (Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures) va GHG Protokol atrofida yaqinlashmoqda.

EU Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) 2026-yildan to'liq kuchga kirishi bu tendentsiyani yanada tezlashtiradi: O'zbekiston kabi EU ga eksport qiluvchi mamlakatlar o'z uglerod baholash tizimlarini EU standartlariga yaqinlashtirishga majbur bo'ladi [5].

4. MUHOKAMA

Olingan natijalar bir qancha muhim xulosalarni beradi, ular mavjud ilmiy adabiyot bilan qisman mos, qisman farqlanadi.

Birinchidan, Navoiy loyidasidagi 6,1 foizlik IRR/ERR farqi Stern (2007) [3] va Boardman (2018) [12] ning nazariy bashoratlari bilan to'liq uyg'un: ekologik tashqi ta'sirlarni monetizatsiya

qilish yashil loyihalar samaradorligini sezilarli oshiradi. Bu natija shuningdek World Bank (2020) ning rivojlanayotgan mamlakatlarda yashil loyihalar uchun ijtimoiy CBA ni qo'llash zaruriyati haqidagi tavsiyasini [11] empirik jihatdan tasdiqlaydi.

Ikkinchidan, konvergentsiya tendentsiyasi OECD (2023) [13] tomonidan ta'kidlangan global standartlashtirishga intilish bilan mos keladi. Biroq bu konvergentsiya hali to'liq emas — uglerod narxlar darajasidagi katta farqlar (EU €85-100 va Xitoy \$8-10 orasida 10 barobarlik farq) metodologiyalarning amaliy natijalarida sezilarli farqlanishni saqlab qolmoqda.

Uchinchidan, Cape Wind (Massachusetts) loyihasining metodologik jihatdan musbat NPV ga ega bo'lishiga qaramay bekor qilinishi shuni ko'rsatadiki, baholash metodologiyasi yetariligi zarur, lekin yetarli shart emas. Institutsional va siyosiy muhit ham hal qiluvchi ahamiyatga ega [4]. O'zbekiston uchun bu xulosa ayniqsa muhim: metodologiyani takomillashtirish bilan bir vaqtda institutsional muhitni ham mustahkamlash zarur.

To'rtinchidan, Xitoy modelining Three Gorges loyihasida EBS bali 92/100 bo'lishiga qaramay jiddiy DNSH muammolarini ko'rsatishi [7] yuqori raqamli baholash ballining loyihaning haqiqiy ekologik samaradorligini kafolatlamasligini isbotlaydi. Bu holat O'zbekiston uchun ogohlantiruvchi dars: milliy baholash tizimini yaratishda greenwashingga qarshi mexanizmlarni dastlabki bosqichdanoq kiritish zarur.

Tadqiqotning cheklovlari quyidagilar: O'zbekiston uchun milliy SCC qiymati rasman belgilanmagan — \$30-50/tCO₂ taxminiy qiymat ishlatildi; empirik tahlil faqat bitta loyihada (Navoiy) o'tkazildi; O'zbekiston statistik ma'lumotlar bazasining cheklanganligi ekologik zararlar monetizatsiyasini qiyinlashtiradi.

5. XULOSA

An'anaviy moliyaviy ko'rsatkichlar (NPV, IRR) yashil investitsiya loyihalarini baholashda yetarli emas. Navoiy quyosh elektrostansiyasida kengaytirilgan ERR (14,2%) moliyaviy IRR dan (8,1%) 6,1 foiz yuqori bo'lib, ekologik va ijtimoiy foydalarni hisobga olish loyiha samaradorligi bahosini sezilarli o'zgartiradi. Bu birinchi gipotezani tasdiqlaydi.

To'rtta xalqaro metodologiya o'rtasida TCFD, ISSB va GHG Protokol atrofida konvergentsiya tendentsiyasi kuzatilmoqda. EU CBAM 2026-yildan kuchga kirishi bu tendentsiyani tezlashtiradi. Bu ikkinchi gipotezani tasdiqlaydi.

O'zbekiston uchun optimal yondashuv: EU Taxonomy asosidagi milliy yashil tasnif (NGET), AQSh CBA/LCOE moliyaviy metodologiyasi, Xitoy EBS ekologik foyda baholash tizimi va Koreya bosqichma-bosqich joriy etish tajribasini birlashtirgan gibrid model.

O'zbekistonda milliy SCC ni belgilash, NGET ni kengaytirish va uglerod narxlar mexanizmini bosqichma-bosqich joriy etish ustuvor vazifalar hisoblanadi.

Kelajakdagi tadqiqotlar uchun: O'zbekiston iqlimiy zaiflik modellari asosida milliy SCC ni hisoblash; UZ-GreenScore modelini 5-10 ta real loyihada sinab, empirik asosda vaznlarni kalibrlash; Markaziy Osiyo mintaqaviy yashil baholash standartlarini uyg'unlashtirish imkoniyatlarini o'rganish tavsiya etiladi.

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